

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Diallel analysis at critical growth stages of rice

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We investigated the genetics of P tolerance across critical growth stages. IR28, IR29, and IR30 and local varieties Khonorullo, Mirikrak, Pawnbuh, and Ngoba were crossed in a diallel fashion without reciprocals.

The F₁ and parental lines were sown in P-deficient soil (available P = 5 ppm, pH = 5.0, soil:water = 2:5), in a randomized block design with three replications. Data on days to germination, flowering, maturity, and duration between flowering and maturity were analyzed following Griffing model 1, method 2.

Differences between the parental and the F₁ lines were significant (see table). Involvement of both additive and nonadditive gene actions was shown by a significant variance of general combining ability (gca) and specific combining ability (sca).

In days to germination, the parents were in two groups: 3 d (IR28, IR30, Khonorullo, and Pawnbuh) and 5 d (IR29, Mirikrak, and Ngoba). Earliness was dominant, but no hybrids were earlier than 3 d. In some crosses, the good general combiners Khonorullo, Mirikrak, and Ngoba, with significant positive gca effects, showed delayed germination. Other nonfixable components revealed less chance of isolating recombinants for early germination.

On the basis of early germination, the parental lines could be arranged as IR28 > IR30 > Mirikrak > Khonorullo > IR29 > Pawnbuh > Ngoba. Early × late crosses showed the dominance of earliness, supported by significant negative sca estimates. Late germination of early × early crosses and their significant positive sca estimates indicate the presence of nonallelic interaction.

Parents with significant gca effects were good combiners, revealing additive action. The gca of parental lines IR28, IR30, Khonorullo, and Mirikrak were in a negative direction.

Proportionately, higher nonfixable components for days to flowering and maturity indicate that improvement of the trait would require quite high selection pressure; however, they indicate little significance for genetic improvement of the character. ■

Estimates of gca and sca effects for duration of critical growth stages in diallel crosses.^a Port Blair, India.

	Days to germination	Days to flowering	Days to maturity	Days from flowering to maturity
<i>Parent^b</i>				
IR28	-0.81**	-4.53**	-3.74**	0.74*
IR29	-0.03	1.24**	4.74**	3.42**
IR30	-0.85**	-2.53**	-2.34**	0.13
Khonorullo	0.19**	-0.95**	-3.67**	-2.53**
Mirikrak	0.60**	4.04**	-5.73*	-1.71**
Pawnbuh	-0.25**	1.40**	3.44**	2.01**
Ngoba	1.15**	9.40**	7.30**	-2.06**
Sji	0.07	0.29	0.28	0.37
S (gi - gi)	0.10	0.44	0.42	0.56
			<i>sca effect^c</i>	
	IR28/Khonorullo (-0.49*)	IR28/Khonorullo (-6.23**)	IR28/Mirikrak (-2.75**)	IR28/IR29 (-2.11*)
	IR28/Ngoba (-1.46**)	IR29/Mirikrak (-6.21**)	IR29/Pawnbuh (-4.70**)	IR28/Mirikrak (-2.28*)
	IR29/Mirikrak (-1.68**)	IR29/Pawnbuh (-4.34**)	IR29/Ngoba (-8.55**)	IR29/Khonorullo (-11.85**)
	IR29/Pawnbuh (-0.83**)	IR29/Ngoba (-7.34**)	IR30/Khonorullo (-9.51**)	IR30/Ngoba (-4.03**)
	IR29/Ngoba (-2.23**)	IR30/Khonorullo (-9.23**)	Mirikrak/Pawnbuh (-18.23**)	Khonorullo/Mirikrak (-3.01**)
	Khonorullo/Pawnbuh (-1.06**)	IR30/Pawnbuh (-6.88**)	Pawn/Ngoba (-6.95**)	Mirikrak/Pawnbuh (-6.85**)
	-	Khonorullo/Ngoba (-6.45**)	-	Pawnbuh/Ngoba (-8.20**)
	-	Mirikrak/Pawnbuh (-11.36**)	-	-
Sij	0.19	0.83	0.81	1.07

^a*, ** = significant at the 5% and 1% levels, respectively. ^bNgoba had the highest P uptake followed by Mirikrak, IR29, IR28, Khonorullo, Pawnbuh, and IR30. ^cOnly important combinations.

Inheritance of flag leaf fresh weight in rice

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Leaf fresh weight (FW) is one indicator of leaf water status. We studied the inheritance of the flag leaf FW in upland rice varieties IAC25, Acc. 36151, Qinai, and Qinnong 2 and lowland rice cultivars Heijiang 8, Hanjiu, N86-18, and Sachimiori. The F₁, F₂, F₃ and their parents were dry seeded in upland. Flag leaf FW dur-

ing heading was measured indirectly at 1400-1600 h (Beijing summer time) using a beta ray gauge (Model XQ-02A).

F₂ and F₃ distributions tended to be continuous, suggesting that flag leaf FW in rice is controlled by multiple genes (see figure).

In the crosses N86-18/Qinnong 2 and Qinaï/Sachiminori, the correlation coefficients (*r*) of flag leaf FW between F₂ and

F₃ populations were not significant, and their heritability in a broad sense [(h_b²)] estimated by linear regression coefficient (b) was 0.1478 and 0.1620, respectively (see table).

Estimated by the formula

$$h_b^3 = \frac{V_{F2} - 1/2 (V_{p1} + V_{p2})}{V_{F2}}$$

the h_b² of the flag leaf FW in cross

Distribution and means of parent, F₂, and F₃ plants for flag leaf fresh weight in 4 crosses, Beijing, China.

r and h_b² of flag leaf FW between F₂ and F₃ populations. Beijing, China.

Cross	<i>r</i>	Sr	t	t 0.05,28	h _b ²
N86-18/Qinnong 2	0.3429	0.1775	1.9318	2.048	0.1478
Qinaï/Sachiminori	0.2301	0.1893	1.2512	2.048	0.1620

IAC25/Hanjiu was 0.4284, and that in cross Hejiang 8/Acc. 36151 was 0.1521. The low h_b² implies that little progress would be expected of selection for this character in early generations. ■

Breeding methods

Effect of *Luffa cylindrica* Roem exudate on plantlet induction from rice anthers

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We investigated the effect of towel gourd extract in the growth medium on inductive efficiency and differentiation frequency of green plantlets in rice anther culture. Test materials were seven japonica and four indica varieties.

Basal induction medium N6, with 2 mg 2,4-D/liter and 60 g sucrose/liter, pH 5.8, was used. The exudate was obtained by cutting the gourd stem. Exudate concentrations were 0, 10, 15, 20, and 25%.

Calli 2-3 mm in diameter were transferred to the differentiation medium (Murashige and Skoog's basal salts with 2 mg kinetin/liter, 0.5 mg NAA/liter, 0.5 mg IAA/liter, and 3% sucrose, pH 5.8).

Callus formation in media with exudate appeared 30-45 d after plating;

Effect of *Luffa cylindrica* exudate in induction medium on callus induction and plant regeneration in rice anther culture.^a Shanghai, China.

Exudate (% vol/vol)	Callus induction (%)	Plant regeneration (%)
<i>Japonica (mean of 7 varieties)</i>		
0	8.56 b	56.70 c
10	12.26 b	69.85 b
15	14.42 a	85.57 a
20	16.69 a	83.10 ab
25	9.29 b	68.93 b
<i>Indica (mean of 4 varieties)</i>		
0	5.41 b	27.05 b
15	6.96 ab	44.84 ab
20	7.01 a	45.48 a

^a In a column within a subspecies, numbers with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.